

Novel Strategies for Maintaining Durable Global Peace: Establishing Politician Rankings and Measuring the Significance of Political Ethics in Global Governance

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Abstract

Politicians are people who hold and exercise political power. Over the past 100 years, the global public has witnessed countless politicians manufacturing lies, chaos or distorting facts for their own interests, and using the media to disseminate false information to deceive voters, resulting in long-term poverty and economic crises in certain countries and regions, with ongoing regional conflicts and wars. Frequent lying by politicians has adverse effects on mental health and families. The public and the United Nations have struggled to restrain the egregious behaviour of subpar politicians. Until now, society as a whole lacked a quantitative evaluation standard for politicians. The article proposes a scientific system to evaluate politicians' integrity and conduct quantitative research on their behavior. By examining the frequency of lying and integrity levels, politicians can be ranked in a 16-level system. This objective assessment aims to identify and distinguish between inferior and exemplary politicians, and ultimately reduce the chances of dishonest politicians coming to power. By regulating the behaviour of politicians, a new political environment and a new political ecosystem based on integrity and stability can be established. This would significantly reduce the threat of lies to regional and global peace, increase the number of global champion of peace, decrease conflicts and wars, and promote global peace and sustainable development. Ultimately, the goal is to realize the aspiration of Mr. Nobel for human peace. If a media establishes a ranking of politicians based on their frequency of lying in different regions, it is likely to become the world's number one media. In addition, it is suggested that Swedish institutions consider establishing a Nobel Prize or a Global Prize in Ethics.

Keywords: war; world peace; ethnic conflict; strategy; ethics; global governance; lying; chaos; national governance; government consensus; the UN declaration; global consensus; politician; statesman; sustainable development; ranking; long-COVID ; COVID-19 ; mask; pandemic; burden; healthcare; moral; comparative ethics; comparative political parties; metrological comparative political parties; metrological comparative politics; sequelae; metrological governmental ethics; metrological political ethics ; metrological politician ethics; metrological statesman ethics; metrological party ethics; metrological political party ethics; metrological judicial ethics; metrological legal ethics; metrological military ethics; the Nobel Peace Prize; political eco-civilization; massacre; telecommunication fraud; organ harvesting; torture; justice; conscience; management; political ecosystem; peace fighter; political ethics; human trafficking; metrological administrative ethics;

Metrological politician or statesman ethics

1. Wearing masks to prevent COVID-19 infection is ridiculed and questioned by many western politicians, and the huge burden of medical care

In the 21st century, when the COVID-19 broke out, although the number of college graduates with higher education in Europe and the United States today is at least 100 times that of the early 20th century, the behavior of wearing masks to prevent COVID-19 infection has been repeatedly treated by many Western politicians with a negative, derisive, questioning or stopping attitude [1,2]. When I see these comments and actions coming out all the time, it amazes me beyond measure. Wearing masks to prevent viral infection is common knowledge in disease prevention, and we've known that since middle school. Why are politicians who have received Western higher education lower in intelligence than Chinese middle school students? Among the three classical elements mentioned in infectious disease textbooks, cutting off transmission routes and protecting vulnerable populations are two very important aspects [3]. Wearing a mask is a common, simple, and effective means of preventing infectious diseases for infectious disease doctors. At the beginning of the 20th century, masks were widely and effectively used to prevent and control the deadly infectious disease Pestis [4,5], with remarkable results. The inventor of the mask has even been nominated for the Nobel Prize in Medicine [4]. Universities in Europe and the United States make up the majority of the world's top 300, and most of the world's top ten medical schools are also in Europe and the United States. We cannot understand why politicians with higher education in Europe and the United States ignore the basic knowledge of preventive medicine and reverse black and white. Instead of requiring the public to take physical isolation to control the pandemic as soon as possible, they take the "lying down" policy to deal with the explosive COVID-19 that scientists have identified, even allowing anti-intellectual behavior such as burning masks on the streets. This resulted in tens of millions of people in European and American countries becoming infected due to the lack of effective physical isolation, resulting in the loss of millions of lives. This is despite the fact that the author is good at preventing COVID-19 infection and can usually significantly improve symptoms in severe patients within 2-4 hours. Even so, when the author spent time in the wards of COVID-19 infected people, he did not dare to wear a mask all the time and was still in awe of COVID-19. So, during the epidemic, the author tested negative for nucleic acid or antigen every time and never tested positive.

According to the study, 23.7 percent of patients with early infection had long-term sequelae, and the risk of long-COVID infection was 3.45 times higher among hospitalized patients than among non-hospitalized patients⁶. Even mild COVID-19 can cause brain aging for up to ten years. According to a Brookings report, 16.3 million people of working age in the United States are suffering from long-COVID, and 4 million are unable to work due to the disease [7]. Conservatively speaking, the estimated annual loss is \$168-230 billion. When the decline in care costs and consumption related to long-COVID is included, it adds an additional \$544 billion. If the United States uses non-interference herd immunization methods, the total burden over the next decade could reach \$17-94 trillion, which is equivalent to 8% to 43% of

the annual tax burden [8]. In the United States alone, the total cost of COVID-19 death and morbidity will reach \$5.5-5.9 trillion in 2020 [9]. It can be seen that the "lying flat" policy formulated by American politicians will bring a huge burden to future healthcare.

2. Confusion over the behavior of lying politicians in Europe and the United States and Oxford English's definition of politicians

In China, most families attach great importance to the education of moral character for future generations. For instance, the education of posterity to be kind to their parents, to cultivate their moral character, to honor their ancestors, to be industrious and thrifty, to be benevolent, faithful, and just, and to be united in knowledge and practice. Among them, teaching children to be honest is one of the important aspects of home education. Although I am not particularly concerned about politics, seeing media coverage of common sense breaking and frequent lying by politicians in Europe and America during the epidemic broke my understanding that senior politicians in a country must have good character, and at the same time, it also left me puzzled about why it is difficult for politicians in Europe and America who have good character and do not lie to appear in the top leadership position. Moreover, during the US presidential election process in recent years, classmates who had voted and worked in the US were very angry that politicians often lied regardless of the basic facts. This also sparked discussions between the author and friends living in the West about the definition of politicians and statesman, and led to the idea of whether different politicians and politicians need to be cognitively distinguished and hierarchical management implemented.

When the author talked about "statesman" with American friends, they mentioned that the American people often use "politician" instead of "statesman" in daily life and think that politicians are liars. Many Chinese have long been conditioned to think of "statesman" as a purely commendatory term and the word "politician" as derogatory meaning from former English learning. A statesman is a man with a certain political vision and political ability, with altruistic thoughts, who can develop the country, seek welfare for the people, uphold world peace, and selflessly devote his youth and even his life to the country or humanity. This is the complete opposite of the Oxford English Dictionary(OED)'s self-serving pejorative interpretation in Article 2 about "politician" [10-12]. The OED defines a politician as "a. A schemer or plotter; a shrewd, sagacious, or crafty person. In later use also (esp. U.S. derogatory, influenced by sense A. 2b): a self-interested manipulator, whose behavior is likened to that of a professional politician." However, a selfish politician can never be a virtuous person. Hillary Clinton's famous quote illustrates the difference between a politician and a statesman: "The difference between a politician and a statesman is that a politician thinks about the next election while the statesman thinks about the next generation." [13]

3. Frequent lying by politicians has adverse effects on mental health and families

In modern politics, the integrity and authenticity of politicians are among the top concerns of voters. Unfortunately, in the pursuit of social influence, strategic misinformation often trumps honesty,¹⁴ leading to frequent lying by some Western politicians, which has negative consequences for mental health and family relationships

[15-17].

First, frequent lies by politicians have brought about mental health issues to the public [15-17]. Lying can cause confusion about the truthfulness of lies. When government and political leaders consistently lie, trust of the public is undermined, resulting in significant confusion and anxiety. Disappointment and despair about politics may lead to skepticism about the decision-making process [18].

Second, frequent lying also has negative effects on the mental health and families of politicians themselves [15-17]. Research has shown that chronic lying and deceitful behavior can trigger psychological stress, anxiety, guilt, or even higher blood pressure. Politicians often face immense pressure and societal expectations, and frequent lying only increases their stress and insecurity. This can lead to mental health issues or even the development of psychological disorders.

The dishonest behavior of politicians can lead to disappointment, suspicion, and alienation among family members.¹⁷ Loss of trust can damage intimate relationships, causing family conflicts and instability. Research has shown that an unstable family environment has a significant impact on the growth and development of children and adolescents, potentially leading to negative behaviors and mental health issues. The high rate of lying found in studies may be caused by a minority of prolific liars, resulting in politicians' families, particularly their adolescent children, becoming more prone to lying [19,20].

Studies have found a negative correlation between telling the truth and re-election in local government elections, suggesting that dishonesty may help politicians survive in office [21]. This highlights the need for the global public to collectively work towards changing the dire state of global politics

4. Politics, Politicians or Statesman and Metrological Party Ethics etc.

The author constantly ponders the broad terms used by Americans to refer to politicians, and the definition of a politician in the Oxford English Dictionary, and is so deeply engrossed in his musings that he cannot help further rationalizing his own reflections. Politics, as a widely applied subject in many American universities, has become a widely cultivated subject for political fraudsters or self-serving manipulators based on the above circumstances. The author can't help but feel a bit shocked and uneasy. The leadership of a region, country, or international organization in the world is almost controlled by statesmen or politicians. They are guiding the prevention and control of the current severe COVID-19 pandemic. Almost all things, processes, or economies in the world are governed or influenced by them. Judicial appointments or judicial administration may also be led by them. More importantly, politics, statesmen, or politicians often lead military or military operations in a country or region. They are almost all leaders. Military operations ultimately determine the lives and deaths of innocent people and whether the world is a peaceful place. Political justice and conscience can promote military justice, maintain world order and peace, and prevent uncontrolled armies from plundering wealth and killing civilians like bandit groups. Emphasizing administrative ethics or political ethics in day-to-day work can help further guide judicial conduct to ethics, guide military behavior to conform to ethics,

guide military behavior to conform to ethics, or use comparative ethics, comparative political parties, metrological comparative political parties, metrological comparative politics, comparative prisoner of war ethics, metrological governmental ethics, metrological political ethics, metrological politician ethics, metrological party ethics(metrological political party ethics), metrological judicial ethics, metrological legal ethics, or metrological military ethics, or metrological war ethics, prisoner of war ethics, or metrological prisoner of war ethics to evaluate the legitimacy of government, politics, statesmen, or politician's actions [22,23].^{1A-9A}

The Chinese subconsciously believe that political figures or leaders should have good morals, cultivation and leadership skills, rather than egoism, which was considered a very important trait and political cultural and moral gene in ancient China. In 686 BC [24], according to Guoyu Qiyu's records, Qi Huanggong would appoint Bao Shuya as prime minister after inheriting the throne. However, Bao Shuya refused and said, "I am just a mediocre courtier of yours. You take care of me so that I do not suffer from cold and hunger. I am already very lucky. If you want to govern the country, it's not what I'm good at. Only Guan Zhong can manage the country." He sincerely said to Qi Huanggong, "I am inferior to Guan Zhong in five aspects: I am inferior to him in pacifying the people with lenience and kindness; I'm not as good as he in governing the country without forgetting the root; I am not as good as he in being faithful and honest and gaining the trust of the people; making etiquette is enough to make the world follow suit, and I'm not as good as him." Although Guan Zhong almost killed Qi Huanggong with an arrow not long ago, he was his enemy. After Bao Shuya persuaded him, Qi Huanggong happily worshipped Guan Zhong as prime minister. This makes Guan Zhong one of the most famous prime ministers in Chinese history. Guan Zhong firmly believes that propriety, righteousness, honesty and shame are the foundation of governing the country. The Chinese people today are deeply influenced by ancient Chinese historical figures and believe that political leaders or political groups should have a sense of justice, goodness or responsibility.

Song Dynasty Premier Fan Zhongyan was a role model for Chinese politicians [25]. He told the people from the point of view of state administrators that they should worry about the country and the people regardless of their personal circumstances and prioritize the interests of the country and the people. He advocated the idea that "one should be concerned about one's country and people before anything else, he should be the first to bear hardships and the last to enjoy" and the moral character of a person with lofty ideals; it has had a profound impact on China's political culture and future generations. Most people may find it hard to imagine that the political leaders or groups of a democratic country, or their leading figures, would want to spread lies, wage unjust wars, or invade the territories of other countries. Instead, amid the hubbub, many Chinese people naturally make historical comparisons, perhaps thinking they are even inferior to the feudal dynasties of China 2,000 years ago.

The author believes that human society needs a practical and universal evaluation standard for leaders based on justice, kindness, and conscience, which includes the transparency and openness of governments and political figures in their governance, ideology, and information dissemination. Due to differences in viewpoints, each

country has formed many political parties, some of which have become ruling parties, some have become opposition parties, and they govern a country or region in different ways.

However, over the past 100 years, the global public has seen more and more unscrupulous politicians lying, creating chaos, or distorting facts for their own interests, and using the media to spread unethical information to bewilder voters or the public. These are one of the root causes of regional economic decline, instability, violence, conflict, military expansion, or war outbreak, and have destroyed brotherhood among some countries. The pursuit of power by unscrupulous politicians often aims to become the leader of a department, region, or country. Their lies and power can become a means for interest groups to disrupt peace and plunder huge resources of other countries by initiating wars. It is also one of the important factors that have led to a significant increase in the world's refugee population. Although the Nobel Peace Prize has been awarded for over a hundred years, the fundamental issues of global peace and the increasing number of refugees have not been resolved or improved [22,26]. Some politicians are exceptionally greedy, fabricate lies, and claim territories that do not belong to their own country as their own. The people of that region have completely different customs and traditions from the country, leading to the creation of wars. Forcing different ethnic groups, who do not share common values, to form a nation has resulted in 70 years of civil war, rampant opium and drug abuse, large-scale consecutive gang rapes, organ harvesting or human trafficking, and mass killings, all of which are crimes against humanity [27].

This means that significant breakthroughs are needed to achieve global security governance or maintaining global peace. As there are many unscrupulous politicians threatening world peace, it is very necessary to improve their moral standards and change the current structure of politicians. Quantitative assessment of the ethical standards of the ruling government and ruling or participating parties using quantitative government ethics or quantitative party ethics methods should be valuable in reducing wars and maintaining world peace [22,23].

If politicians and statesmen can be distinguished and graded according to the idea of metrological politician ethics, metrological governmental ethics, etc. [22,23], allowing great politicians, noble statesmen, or their groups to stand out, and true statesmen are not restricted by capital to realize their great or lofty political ideals or ideals to manage the institutions of government power, they would make the world more peaceful, economically stable, socially orderly, and people happier.

The greatest threat to human survival and lasting peace is inferior politicians. Technological progress does not necessarily lead to civilizational advancement. Only by significantly reducing the presence of inferior politicians in politics can human civilization make significant progress, and a new political ecological civilization system can be established globally.

The author believes that the establishment of a new discipline centered on metrological political ethics, metrological politician ethics, metrological governmental ethics or metrological party ethics is beneficial to the construction of an objective [22,23], fair, reasonable, and sixteen-level management system or a new political eco-

civilization system that can evaluate the system and distinguish great statesman, distinguished statesman, outstanding statesman, excellent statesman, noble statesman, honest statesman, diligent statesman, statesmen, political personnel, politician and political swindlers (Table 1), combined with quantitative military ethics or quantitative prisoner-of-war ethics assessments. This will greatly reduce the threat of lies by politicians or political rascals to regional and world peace, reduce the number of saboteurs for global peace, rapidly cultivate and increase the number of global peace fighters, widely promote a culture of peace, significantly reduce the number or intensity of conflicts or wars and reduce the number of refugees. It is expected to make significant contributions to world peace and stability, economic prosperity, and people's well-being. In addition, using metrological political ethics, metrological politician ethics, metrological governmental ethics and metrological party ethics as the basis for establishing a hierarchical evaluation standard for politicians and statesmen is not only conducive to the selection of the Nobel Peace Prize or the World Peace Prize, reducing long-standing disputes, but also improving the governance level of some countries or regions.

Table 1. Classification of Statesman or Political staffs or Politicians★

No.	Different levels of Political staffs	Notes
1	Great statesman	Its contents may be more suitable for people to write.
2	Distinguished statesman	Its contents may be more suitable for people to write.
3	Outstanding statesman	A statesman with conscience, sincerity, truthfulness, pragmatism, foresight, selflessness, and good organizational, management, and leadership skills; a statesman who allows people to experience judicial justice, high administrative efficiency, clean government, a thriving economy in various industries, and enjoy a good and prosperous life; A statesman who oppose the manufacture and use of biological and chemical weapons, such as bacteria and viruses, have never publicly encouraged or instigated or ordered a party to a conflict in a country or region to use radioactive weapons and munitions, such as depleted uranium bombs, with the exception of countries that initiated World War II where radioactive weapons were used, have never publicly advocated or ordered the use of their own force to overthrow the legitimate government of another country, and have never advocated or ordered the pillage of another country's territory.
4	Noble statesman	A statesman of conscience, honesty, pragmatism, positivity, impartiality, high moral character, good management skills, and selflessness; A statesman who actively engages in politics, has

		ideals, is able to think for the country and the people, and is motivated by a focus on people's well-being, world peace and development. He did not treat similar matters with double standards, did not actively create conflicts and conflicts between regions or nations, respected historical facts, opposed the manufacture and use of biological and chemical weapons such as bacteria and viruses, never encourages or instigates or orders one party to a conflict in a country or region to first use radioactive weapons and ammunition such as depleted uranium bombs, with the exception of countries that initiated World War II where radioactive weapons were used, and never publicly advocates or orders the overthrow of the legitimate regime of another country with the force of his own country, never claimed or ordered the plundering of another country's territory.
5	Excellent	A statesman with political ideals, conscience, sincerity, selflessness, pragmatism, vision, and ability to govern and lead well; a statesman who allows people to experience judicial fairness, high administrative efficiency, clean government, economic prosperity, and peaceful living and working; a statesman who is able to think for the country and the people and whose motivation is focused on the well-being of the people, world peace and development.
6	Fair-minded statesman	A statesman with conscience, truthfulness, pragmatism, fairness, impartiality, high administrative efficiency, honesty and friendliness to the people.
7	Honest statesman	A statesman with conscience, truthfulness, pragmatism, fairness, selflessness, honesty and friendliness to the people.
8	Diligent or practical statesman	A statesman with conscience, truth-telling, practical work, foresight, good organization and management, fair administration, high administrative efficiency, good faith and affinity to the people, and a prosperous economy.
9	Statesman	A righteous politician with foresight who serves the country and the people. "A politician thinks of the next election. A statesman, of the next generation." – James Freeman Clarke
10	Political staff	People who regards elected political office or position as a profession.
11	Politician	Politicians who meet any of the following ① or ② or ③. ① Politicians who lie or spread rumors to the public 1-3 times in 6 months; ② or politicians who deal with similar matters with double standards. ③ Failure to follow logical identity law in dealing with international incidents.
12	Mosquito-level Politician	Politicians who meet any of the following ①-⑥ ① Politicians who lie or spread rumors to the public 4-6 times in 6 months; ② or politicians who repeatedly deal with similar

		<p>matters with double standards; ③ politicians who create conflicts or contradictions, or wars between regions or countries against historical facts; ④ politicians who ignore the oppression of vulnerable groups by their subordinates; ⑤ politicians who disregard the interests and lives of vulnerable people; ⑥ or the politicians who ignore judicial injustice.</p>
13	Bedbug - level Politician	<p>Politicians who meet any of the following (1) or (2). (1) Politicians who lie or spread rumors to the public 7-9 times in 6 months; (2) or politicians who personally participate in or organize personnel or condone others to maliciously destroy or set fire to public property, or unfairly and illegally destroy or plunder others' property, or beating, killing, or unlawfully detaining an individual, once within 12 months, 1-3 times within 36 months, resulting in a total loss of 1 million to 2 million RMB or 200,000 to 400,000 US dollars or € 200,000 to 400,000 euros, or causing one death or 4-7 injuries.</p>
14	Hornet -level Politician	<p>Politicians who meet any of the following (1) or (2). (1) Politicians who lie or spread rumors to the public 10-12 times in 6 months; (2) or politicians who personally participate in or organize personnel or condone others to maliciously destroy or set fire to public property, or unfairly and illegally destroy or plunder others' property, or beating, killing, or unlawfully detaining an individual, once within 12 months, 1-3 times within 36 months, resulting in a total loss of 2 million to 5 million RMB or 400,000 to 1,000,000 USD or 400,000 to 1,000,000 euros, or causing 2 death or 8-12 injuries.</p>
15	Parasite level Politician	<p>Politicians who meet any of the following conditions: ① Politicians who are double-faced and often treat similar matters with double standards; ② Politicians who enjoy creating conflicts or contradictions, or launching wars between regions or countries based on historical facts; ③ Politicians who condone subordinates and oppress vulnerable groups; ④ Politicians who design methods to seize the interests of vulnerable groups; ⑤ Politicians who have the power to propose amendments to their domestic laws and regulations, knowing that they are clearly unfair and prone to disputes. ⑥ Politicians who spread rumors about major events.</p>
16	Rat-level Politician	<p>Politicians who meet any of the following (1) or (2). ① Politicians who lied or spread rumors to the public 13 to 15 times in a six-month period; ② politicians who personally participate in or organize personnel or condone others to maliciously destroy or set fire to public property, or unfairly and illegally destroy or plunder others' property, or beating, killing, or unlawfully detaining an individual, 1-2 times within 12 months,</p>

		1-3 times within 36 months, causing a total loss of 5 million to 10 million RMB, 1 million to 3 million USD, or 1 million to 3 million euros, or causing 3 deaths or 13-20 injuries.
17	Fox -level Politician	Politicians who meet any of the following (1) or (2). ①Politicians who lied or spread rumors to the public 16 to 25 times in a 12 month period; ② politicians who personally participate in or organize personnel or condone others to maliciously destroy or set fire to public property, or unfairly and illegally destroy or plunder others' property, or beating, killing, or unlawfully detaining an individual, 1-2 times within 12 months, 1-3 times within 36 months, causing a total loss of 10 to 40 million RMB or 3 to 10 million USD or 3 to 10 million euros or more, or causing 4-8 deaths or 20-50 injuries.
18	Crocodile - level Politician	Crocodile-level Politicians who meet any of the following ①or ②or③. ①Politicians who lied or spread rumors to the public more than 30 times in a 12-month period. ②Politicians who personally participate in or organize personnel or condone others to maliciously destroy or set fire to public property, or unfairly and illegally destroy or plunder others' property, or beating, killing, or unlawfully detaining an individual, once or more within 12 months, 1-3 times or more within 36 months, causing a total loss of 40 million CNY, 10 million USD, 10 million euros or more, or causing 9 or more deaths or 50 or more injuries.③Often telling lies, handling similar matters with double standards, creating or maintaining conflicts and contradictions between regions or countries in violation of historical facts, and attempting to split the country through military confrontation in the handling of its internal affairs.
19	Shark-level Politician	Shark-level destructive inferior politician: Politician who violate historical facts and attempt to plunder the land of other countries by improper means or force, constantly creating conflicts and wars.
20	Hippo-level inferior Politician	Inferior politician with one of the following characteristics: ① He or she treats power as an axiom and international law and norms of international relations as nothing; on the surface, believing in religion, but in reality having no faith, has never been "freedom and democracy", but "putting interests first", for his or her personal gain, his or her depravity and greed can exceed the imagination of ordinary people. His or her shamelessness can push the limits of humanity, creating nothing out of nothing, twisting black and white, and lying and spreading rumors can be considered the pinnacle. "he or her incites chaos, sow discord, deliberately form cliques, abandon rules, and bully the market

		with almost no limits." he or her persistently fabricates all kinds of lies to divert attention, maliciously malign other countries and mislead international opinion.②Politicians who commanded or participated in the killing of innocent civilians resulting in 500 or more deaths.
21	Devil-level inferior Politician	Devil-level political swindler or inferior politician with one of the following characteristics: ①Politicians who disregard the provisions of the United Nations Charter and participate in organizing, manufacturing or ordering the use of biological or chemical weapons, including bacteria or viruses; ②Politicians who disregard the provisions of the United Nations Charter and order the use of biological and chemical weapons to kill or attempt to kill humanity or cause disasters in other countries or regions. ③Or instigate or order a conflicting party in a national or regional war to use radioactive weapons and munitions such as depleted uranium bombs first, resulting in large numbers of casualties and environmental contamination, with the exception of countries that initiated World War II where radioactive weapons were used. ④Politicians who permit or intentionally release significant amounts of radioactive waste that poses a substantial risk to the local or global environment or ecosystems.⑤. Politicians who commanded or participated in the killing of innocent civilians resulting in 1,000 or more deaths.

★ Statesmen may be able to discuss the ranking of statesmen and politicians. In order to better govern their respective countries, benefit the people, cultivate champions of peace, reduce conflicts and wars, and maintain world peace, statesmen of various countries may be able to negotiate on the certification standards of level 13, 14 and 15 politicians that are easy to reach consensus. If they can reach an agreement, they can gather in Laozi's hometown or Confucius, the ancient sage, to jointly issue the Kuxian Declaration or Qufu Declaration on several standards of the classification of statesmen and politicians in the world; or the Stockholm Declaration in the capital of peace.

★If statesmen of various countries can reach consensus and issue relevant statesmen' declarations or global consensus or global government consensus, it is possible to open a new era in global politics and a new era for world peace. If there is no consensus on what ordinary people think is very bad behavior, it indicates that there may be serious problems in the values of some statesmen or politicians, which is also an opportunity for the global public to improve their understanding of politics or statesmen and politicians.

★The ranking of politicians is dynamic, with each country or district forming a ranking or implementing hierarchical management, or possibly being reclassified every six months or a year according to the situation of the country or region in which it is

located. People are not saints and sages, and those who can correct their mistakes should be encouraged. Anyone who can recognize their own shortcomings and mistakes, continuously improve their own ideological and moral character, and change past misconduct will have a change in the ranking of statesmen or politicians. This is conducive to improving the moral level of global politicians and the governance level of their respective regions. Each region is a part of the world, and improving governance in each region is clearly conducive to world peace and sustainable development. From the point of view of the vast majority of the public in this world, it is believed that there should be more outstanding, honest and practical statesmen who hope to emerge from different countries or regions, rather than politicians. Any statesman or politician who has made mistakes, as long as he can improve his own cultivation, refuses to lie and deceive the public, and does things that are conducive to public and world peace, should also be promoted in the ranking of statesmen or politicians. There are only a very few evil politicians who cause great harm to humanity, commit massacres and cause serious damage to the sustainable development of the Earth. The public usually has a specific and difficult to change ranking and ranking recognition.

5. The value of establishing regional political rankings for the media

If there were a media outlet that established a regional ranking of politicians based on their frequency of lying, not only would the general public be more inclined to browse through that media outlet, but politicians themselves would also pay special attention to it. During elections for positions such as governor, senator, or president, voters would be extremely interested in this ranking. In the realm of politics, this media outlet could potentially become the number one global media outlet.

6. Suggest considering the establishment of the Nobel Prize in Ethics

No matter how advanced science and technology develop, a society lacking moral ethics cannot eliminate human trafficking, organ harvesting, war, and massacre. The progress of science and technology can even facilitate politicians in implementing fraud, torture, war, and massacre. Today, Myanmar is adjacent to China, which has a civilization with thousands of years of tradition. However, the greed of Myanmar politicians and the kindness of Chinese statesmen led to Myanmar politicians forcibly combining the northern region once belonging to China with the Burmese people to form a country. Now, Myanmar looks like a semi-slave society with human trafficking, organ harvesting, war, and massacre rampant in many areas [27]. The Myanmar government and military have become protective umbrellas, and a large amount of criminal evidence has been openly destroyed by the military. The ruling party and politicians in Myanmar refuse to acknowledge their protection of telecommunication fraud and massacre; however, advanced military aircraft such as Su-30 have become tools for the Myanmar government to crackdown on the armed resistance against telecommunication fraud and massacre [27]. This demonstrates the importance of moral ethics in constructing a civilized society.

It is suggested that Swedish institutions consider establishing a Nobel Prize or a

Global Prize in Ethics¹⁴, which specifically rewards the moral and ethical models of the planet except those outside mainland China. Even if the ceremony is held every two years, or every three or four years. It is believed that this will considerably enhance the global public's awareness of moral culture and morality, create more peace fighters, eliminate research on biological weapons such as deadly viruses, reduce the number of conflicts and wars, reduce the number of nuclear weapons and promote world peace. The prize may achieve more valuable practical results than the Nobel Peace Prize. It is believed that this will be very constructive to cultivate values and ethics with “propriety, righteousness, honesty and shame” and “Neither riches nor honours can corrupt him; neither poverty nor humbleness can make him swerve from principle; neither threats nor forces can subdue him”[28], minimizing the chance that chemistry, biotechnology and management talents, etc. trained by universities will become tools for inferior politicians and army-ruffians to manufacture killing biological weapons, and let them take the initiative to unmask these politicians' heinous crimes against humanity.

^{1A} Quantitative political ethics(metrological political ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistical methods to study political ethics issues or phenomena in social and political life, and to conduct quantitative research on political behaviors or moral levels such as justice, conscience, moral character, fairness, honesty, responsibility, legitimacy, efficiency, caring for people, maintaining social order, protecting people, eliminating evil, correcting errors, negative feedback level, rumor making, lying, spreading false information, deliberately creating disputes or conflicts , etc. in the process of spreading or implementing political propositions [22,23].

^{2A} Metrological party ethics (metrological political party ethics) (quantitative party ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistical methods to study ethical issues or phenomena of a political party in modern social and political life, and to conduct quantitative research on its political behavior or moral level in the process of spreading or implementing political ideas [22,23].

^{7A} Metrological administrative or government ethics (quantitative administrative Ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to study ethical issues and moral phenomena in administrative activities, and to conduct quantitative research on administrative behaviors or moral levels such as loyalty, selecting and appointing the virtuous and capable, fairness, justice, conscience, honesty, diligence, integrity, work initiative, governance ability, governance efficiency, transparency, legitimacy, truth-seeking and pragmatic, innovation, promotion of social development, responsibility and inaction, foresight, timeliness and rationality of policies or institutions introduction, loving the people, maintaining social order, protecting the people, protecting the legitimate rights and interests of individuals, eliminating evil, unity and cooperation, coordination, accountability, self-cultivation, self-discipline, self-examination, correction of errors, negative feedback level in

administrative activities [22,23].

^{3A} Metrological comparative politics(quantitative comparative politics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on the theories, norms, problems, behaviors, phenomena, results or laws in different political fields or different aspects of the same political field [22,23].

^{4A} Quantitative comparative political partics (metrological comparative political partics, or metrological comparative partics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on the theories, norms, problems, behaviors, phenomena, results or laws in different political parties or different aspects of the same political party [22,23].

^{5A} Metrological judicial ethics (quantitative judicial ethics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the judicial field [22,23].

^{6A} Metrological legal ethics (quantitative legal ethics): A discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the field of law [22,23].

^{7A} Metrological military ethics (quantitative military ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the military field [22,23].

^{8A} Metrological war ethics (quantitative war ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in warfare [22,23].

^{9A} Quantitative prisoner of war ethics (metrological prisoner of war ethics): An applied discipline that uses mathematical or mathematical statistics methods to conduct quantitative research on moral and ethical issues or phenomena in the prisoner of war field [22,23].

^{10A} Metrological politician or statesman ethics: This is an applied discipline. Its main research method is to use mathematical or mathematical statistical means and focuses on the political ethics issues involved by politicians in social, professional and political activities. Specifically, it conducts quantitative research on various behaviors exhibited by politicians in the process of disseminating or implementing relevant political propositions, covering many aspects, such as justice, conscience, moral character, fairness, impartiality, integrity, sense of responsibility, legality, work efficiency, concern for the people, maintenance of social order, protection of people's rights and interests, punishment of evil phenomena, correction of wrong behaviors and the degree of negative feedback and other positive or positive dimensions. At the same time, it also includes negative or negative behavior manifestations such as starting rumors, deliberately lying, spreading false information, disturbing social order, deliberately causing investment failures, deliberately provoking disputes, triggering conflicts and even starting wars.

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